

IMPLICATIONS OF ACCOUNTING INFORMATION SYSTEM TO FINANCIAL DECISION-MAKING AMONG SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES IN DAET, CAMARINES NORTE

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ABSTRACT

Accounting information system (AIS) is very vital in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). It has various applications in carrying out quality financial decision-making. Hence, this study was conducted to determine the implications of AIS to financial decision-making in SMEs in terms of business strategy and performance improvement. The data were collected from 141 SMEs in Daet, Camarines Norte, using self-made survey questionnaires and the descriptive-correlational method as the research design. Findings revealed that most SMEs are under sole proprietorship, with P3,000,000 to P100,000,000 total assets in 2020, with less than 10 employees, currently in business operation for 3 to 5 years, and with a manual system of AIS. On the implications of SMEs' AIS on financial decision-making in terms of business strategy, AIS serves as a competitive advantage and innovative system that provides timely, reliable, comparable, and quality financial reports. While on the implications of SMEs' AIS on financial decision-making in terms of performance improvement, AIS enables the owners/managers to understand their tasks better and reduce uncertainty before making decisions. Moreover,

all of the indicators regarding the implications of AIS to financial decision-making in terms of business strategy and performance improvement are interpreted as strongly agree. This study rejected the null hypothesis and found a weak positive correlation between total assets in the 2020 SMEs' profile and the implications of SMEs' accounting information systems on financial decision-making. The study formulated strategies to improve the quality of their financial decision-making.

Keywords: *accounting information system, business strategy, financial decision-making, performance improvement, small and medium enterprise (SME)*

INTRODUCTION

Businesses must make the paradigm change to technology-based and online-based transactions to continue to exist and support their operations. Increasing one's proficiency in dealing with financial transactions clears the way for the use of different information systems. One of these information systems is Accounting Information System (AIS). The global business environment has been continuously changing due to rapid technological advancements in production systems, information systems improvements, increasing market rivalry, rising customer expectations, and unprincipled manipulative activities by businesses, particularly the small and medium enterprises (SMEs). In this situation, business dynamics' composite and impulsive nature have highlighted the critical significance of AIS as a major driver of economic and business discourse, especially in financial decision-making and management effectiveness (Hosain, 2019). The AIS utilization by businesses provides a clear direction toward its future goals. Moreover, Meiryani et al. (2020) stated that AIS assists SMEs in making relevant and reliable accounting information. It is conveyed through the firm's financial statements/reports that serve as a conduit of communication between its business operations and parties interested in its financial position and business development. It has various applications that rely on internal and external users, specifically in carrying out quality financial decision-making.

According to National Economic Development Authority (2017), the micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) sector is still struggling with the integration and support analytics of information system in general, and the AIS in particular. These information systems were required to monitor the sector performance and provide a foundation for strategic planning. One of the strategies cited is to improve access to technology and innovation by encouraging innovation and adoption of technologies. Despite its importance, most SMEs in the Philippines have not given sufficient attention to bookkeeping and AIS concerning their firm's activities. This is due to lack of good awareness of owners or corresponding administrators of record-keeping and accounting procedures. The SMEs' problems can be attributed to a lack of an accountable and effective accounting system, low operators' educational experience, and hiring unskilled accounting employees, all of which contribute to misleading accounting or financial statements (Rustiana & Khairunnisa, 2019). In support of this claim, another issue that arose during the interpretation of financial data, financial decision-making, or performance assessment was the lack of a sound or appropriate accounting system (Franklin et al., 2021).

Based on the researchers' interviews with some SMEs in Daet, Camarines Norte, it was revealed that some SMEs in the province fail because of lack funding or working capital and mismanagement of financial resources. It is also challenging to accumulate funds and expand their business because they cannot generate reliable and comparable financial statements for loan approval and finding prospective investors. Some cannot also avail credit in ordering direct materials because the suppliers cannot ensure the business's creditworthiness due to unreliable financial statements. They do not prepare budgets and performance reports to assess whether they are beyond the budget. It is also difficult for them to make quality financial decision-making because of their inability to collect, process, and store accounting information needed to generate reliable, relevant, comparable, timely, and quality financial statements/reports. The head of the Department of Trade and Industry Camarines Norte Field Office and the staff of DTI Go Negosyo in the province of Camarines Norte also confirm this situation.

The research framework was based on the Open Systems Theory premise. According to Von Bertalanffy (1993), Open Systems Theory explores the connections between organizations and their surroundings. Open systems, such as business processes, link (interact) with their environment and should be governed when they become disordered owing to internal subsystem factors. Environmental disturbances are tracked and forecasted through organized systems. Any major or unexpected disruptions seriously threaten the organization's survival. Globalization, liberalization, innovation, technology, law, and conflicts are shifting market dynamics that business organizations must adapt to prosper (International Council on Systems Engineering, 2021).

As a result, the Open System Theory variables, including internal and external factors, influence the organization's environment. It is critical to the current study since these elements affect the organization. Internal environmental circumstances are the controllable factors that the business may intervene on, such as their AIS and performance improvement, as shown on the left side of the diagram. The business strategies relating to competition, technology, innovation, and laws and regulations as shown on the right side of the diagram indicate the external factors. The AIS's financial decision-making consequences may also be used to assess continual feedback and development. All aspects influence the system and may help improve the quality of financial decisions. The figure depicts how the variables investigated in this research are related to SMEs.

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework

The researchers wanted to know the real experiences of SMEs on their AIS and how it can help their financial decision-making. Hence, this study was conducted to identify the business profile of SMEs in terms of total assets in 2020, years in operation, and AIS used. Also, it identified the implications of the AIS on their financial decision-making in business strategy and performance improvement and if there is a significant relationship between SMEs’ profile and the implications of AIS to financial decision-making. Moreover, the researchers proposed strategies based on the implications of AIS for financial decision-making.

METHODOLOGY

The researchers for this study used a descriptive-correlational approach to data collection. Moreover, the total population was 243 SMEs. A statistician determined the sample size for the target group to be 141 using the Krejcie and Morgan Sampling Method and purposive sampling. According to the study's description, the respondents were small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) located in Daet, Camarines Norte, and officially registered with the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) in 2021. Respondents were defined categorically as those who have been in continuous operation for at least three (3) years and have implemented AIS, whether manual, computerized, or using accounting software. The respondents were managers or owners of SMEs in Daet, Camarines Norte.

The researchers designed this study's primary data-collecting instrument as a survey questionnaire. The study questionnaire was broken into three portions that varied in length according to the level of information necessary for analysis. The first section profiled SMEs regarding their total assets in 2020, years in operation, and AIS used. The second section discussed SMEs' AIS while the third section focused on the implications of AIS to their financial decision-making regarding business strategy and performance improvement.

A dry run or pilot test was undertaken to assess the questionnaire's usability and correctness. Twenty (20) SMEs from Daet, Camarines Norte, were used as test subjects. This task helped uncover possible questionnaire errors and validate the questionnaire's validity by demonstrating the consistency of the questions, components, and measurements. The reliability test resulted at 0.863 using Cronbach's alpha, therefore passing. Then it was given to the responders. First, the researchers requested permission from the owner/manager to collect data. After approval, the survey questionnaire included informed consent. It was gathered, collated, and evaluated for precise findings. The researchers assured that the data collected would be used only for academic reasons and kept private. The college's research ethics were scrupulously observed.

The study's results were analyzed and interpreted using statistical tools. Descriptive and correlational statistics were used to analyze quantitative data. Statistical correlations were used to show how closely two variables are linked. The profile of the respondents was determined using percentage frequency distribution. Moreover, the weighted mean was used to quantify the implication of AIS on SMEs' financial decision-making and performance improvement. The weighted mean was used to compare the variables' relative significance. Somer's Delta and Point Biserial Correlations were used to evaluate the relationship between the SMEs' profile and the implications of AIS on their financial decision-making regarding business strategy and performance improvement. An interview was also conducted to validate their responses.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The researchers organized and presented data in tabular format with thorough explanations. Each table includes implications and evidence to back up the assertions. This presentation was made to help explain the statistical data collected. The following data are presented: the business profile, accounting information system (AIS) implications on financial decision-making for business strategy and performance improvement, and the significant relationship between SMEs' profile and the implications of AIS to financial decision-making.

SMEs' Profile

Tables 1 to 3 present the SMEs' profile in terms of the total assets in 2020, the number of years in operation, and the type of accounting information system (AIS) used.

Total Assets in 2020. Table 1 illustrates the SMEs' total assets in 2020. It shows that majority of the respondents had total assets in 2020 of P 3,000,000 to P100,000,000 with a frequency of 132 or 93.62%, while the least number of respondents had P100,000,001 to P350,000,000 total assets in 2020 with a frequency of 9 or 6.38%.

Table 1. Total Assets in 2020

<i>Total Assets Bracket (Php)</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
P 3,000,000 – P100,000,000	132	93.62
P 100,000,001 – P350,000,000	9	6.38
Total	141	100.00

According to the findings, majority of the SMEs in Daet, Camarines Norte have total assets of between P3,000,000 to P100,000,000 in 2020. According to the respondents, they operate with limited assets since that is their financial capability being single proprietors themselves, and they classify their businesses as small firms. According to a Department of Trade and Industry survey – Camarines Norte, there was 96% of small businesses in Daet, Camarines Norte. These small businesses represent the retail, general goods, agribusiness, and service sectors.

In support, Beralde (2020) revealed that 90% of the respondents in Labo, Talisay, and Daet, Camarines Norte, worked for enterprises with total assets above P 3,000,000. The SMEs were able to persevere in the face of business challenges and competition. It means that the small business's assets were adequate to keep operations running, enabling them to stay in business. They are considered in the service, retail, and general goods industries.

However, just a few SMEs in Camarines Norte were identified to have total assets in 2020 ranging from P 100,000,001 to P350,000,001. According to the DTI – Camarines Norte report, medium firms account for 3% of all SMEs in Daet, Camarines Norte. Finance, retailer, transportation services, drugstore/pharmacy, general goods, hardware, auto supply, and cooperative are represented.

This is in line with a study conducted by Tambunan (2019) in the province of Kalimantan, Indonesia, in a town capital similar to Daet. It was discovered that 6% of medium enterprises focused on skilled labor and significant capital, such as electronic goods, automobiles, industrial products, telecommunications, and infrastructure.

Number of Years in Operation. Table 2 illustrates the years in

operation with their corresponding frequency and percentage. It shows that most small and medium-scale entities are currently in business operation for three to five years with a frequency of 59 or 41.84%. It was followed by six to eight years with a frequency of 44 or 31.21%, while the lowest was fifteen and above and twelve to fourteen years of operation with a frequency of 9 or 6.38%, and 10 or 7.09%, respectively.

According to the findings, most respondents have been in business for three to five years. Based on the interviews conducted, these firms are still in the early stages of development. Furthermore, they said they are newcomers to the industry and are gaining business knowledge to identify how to overcome challenges and keep operations running smoothly.

Its findings are similar to those of Rao and Shinozaki (2021), who found that 59.6% of the studied MSMEs have been in operation for less than five years, indicating that they are young start-ups. Most of them are still in their beginnings and have yet to break into the market. It was followed by businesses that have been in existence for six to ten years (18.8%), eleven to fifteen years (8.5%), thirteen to thirty years (9.6%), and more than thirty years (3.4%).

Table 2. Number of Years in Operation

<i>Number of Years in Operation</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
3 – 5	59	41.84
6 – 8	44	31.21
9 – 11	19	13.48
12 – 14	10	7.09
15 and above	9	6.38
Total	141	100.00

A few SMEs have been in operation for 15 years or more, indicating that they are well-established. Furthermore, due to their lengthy operation period, they may continue to operate as fully functional enterprises, demonstrating that there is a demand for the goods or services they provide to clients. They have built a firm name and image in the business world over many years. Despite

the presence of competition, they persevered amidst all business difficulties.

In contrast to this finding, Gumel (2017) found that most SMEs in Lagos fail within five years of their founding, with the percentage of enterprises lasting less than five years being greater. They noted that the fact that a significant proportion of the businesses are over five years old indicates that the survival rate of SMEs is strong and improving.

Type of Accounting Information System Being Used. Table 3 shows the type of Accounting Information System (AIS) being used by the respondents. It indicates that most of the respondents use the manual system of AIS with a frequency of 59 or 41.85%, while the least of the respondents use accounting software with a frequency of 35 or 24.82%.

Table 3. Type of Accounting Information System Being Used

<i>Type of Accounting Information System</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Manual	59	41.85
Computerized	47	33.33
Accounting Software	35	24.82
Total	141	100.00

Most SMEs in Daet, Camarines Norte, use manual AIS systems; nevertheless, SMEs in Daet are also considering computerized AIS systems and accounting software. According to the interview, these organizations use both manual and accounting software interchangeably, with a more significant percentage of SMEs preferring the manual. They often utilize Microsoft Excel as a computerized AIS to account for rental income and sales revenue. However, due to lack of resources, knowledge, and competence in running the system, and the system's inability to be user-friendly, they are not prepared to convert the entire manual or computerized AIS to accounting software. Implementing an efficient AIS aids in the management of their financial data allows them to continue to operate their firm effectively.

Ibrahim et al. (2020) found that most SMEs' financial information processes are manual. They can swiftly calculate their firm rental income and vendor sales revenue in Microsoft Excel for record-keeping. Excel is inexpensive and easy to use for basic computations, according to the respondent.

A small percentage of respondents are taking advantage of data-driven accounting software. According to the respondents in the survey, this software aids them in obtaining high-quality financial data and reports, as well as assisting management in gaining a better understanding of their business. It eventually becomes the foundation for improving their overall performance and strategies. Similarly, Rahman (2016) found that proper AIS software installation and usage may enhance performance. This tool may aid in the competitiveness of SMEs. Finally, accounting software aided business owners and policymakers better understand their company's performance and growth prospects. Accounting software can assist SMEs in making crucial financial decisions by providing reliable and comparable financial data.

Implications of SMEs' Accounting Information System on Financial Decision Making

Tables 4 and 5 show the implications of AIS on SMEs' business strategy and performance. The following tables summarize the data gathered from respondents into weighted means with interpretations.

Business Strategy. Table 4 presents the implications of SMEs' AIS on their financial decision-making regarding business strategy. The AIS's highest indicator is a competitive advantage and innovative system that provides quality financial reports with a weighted mean of 4.90, a verbal interpretation of strongly agree. AIS provides understandable and comparable financial statements that SMEs can pay their bills promptly and have good liquidity for bank loan approval and expansion, with 4.89 interpreted as strongly agree. While the AIS provides quality financial reports to trading partners or suppliers who extend credit got the lowest weighted mean of 4.48.

Table 4. Implications of SMEs’ AIS to Financial Decision-Making along Business Strategy

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. AIS delivers clear and comparative financial reports that help businesses pay their bills on time and have enough liquidity to get bank loans for money accumulation and business growth.	4.89	SA
2. It helps potential investors analyze financial data for capital accumulation and business expansion.	4.84	SA
3. It provides quality financial reports to trade partners/suppliers who grant credit and analyze the firm’s creditworthiness to sustain supplies.	4.48	SA
4. The government uses accurate financial reports to monitor benchmarks like sales revenue and profit to assess each business’s size and compliance with employee, consumer, and safety standards.	4.52	SA
5. It provides prospective staff with vital financial information if the firm is financially prepared to give long-term employment and assistance.	4.50	SA
6. It helps the firm to provide quality products at reduced production costs to customers/clients, resulting in better profits.	4.83	SA
7. It provides credible financial statements to auditors for an independent audit opinion, including stakeholders in business issues and concerns.	4.87	SA
8. It assists external consultants in utilizing and analyzing cost, sales, and revenue data, whether to provide lower initial prices or price revisions that will attract more consumers and product changes.	4.72	SA
9. It helps taxing authorities determine if a firm reported the right amount of tax in its tax filings to avoid fines and closure.	4.88	SA
10. It is a competitive advantage and innovative system that delivers timely, accurate, comparative, and high-quality financial information.	4.90	SA
Average Weighted Mean	4.74	SA

Legend: 4.21-5.00 - Strongly Agree (SA) 1.81-2.60 – Disagree (D)
 3.41-4.20 - Agree (A) 1.00-1.80 - Strongly Disagree (SD)
 2.61-3.40 - Neither Agree nor Disagree (NA or D)

The overall weighted mean average of the implications of SME's AIS to financial decision-making along business strategy is 4.74, and the verbal interpretation strongly agree. The highest result is where SMEs' accounting information system delivers a competitive advantage and an innovative design that generates timely, trustworthy, comparable, and high-quality financial reporting. The respondents said that by using AIS, they had access to accurate and timely financial data that enabled them to make sound business decisions on total sales or losses, expenditures, unanticipated purchases, and billing increases, among other things. These are only a few of the advantages of AIS to firms, which will result in more effective and efficient financial decision-making.

To bolster this conclusion, Hezabr (2018) discovered in his research that effective AIS tries to use contextual information to boost the quantity and quality of data available to users, hence giving a variety of vital information tailored to their specific requirements. Furthermore, integrating operations alone is insufficient in today's competitive company environment since it does not incorporate internal infrastructure and competitive strategy. On the other hand, integrating internal processes with external users is critical for establishing a successful chain.

The second highest indicator is that AIS provides comparable financial reports that assist businesses in paying their payments on time. According to respondents, many banks demand that they provide audited financial statements as a prerequisite for loan approval. Financial statements are used by small and medium-sized businesses to get bank funding and increase their competitiveness.

It is supported by the study of Iswoyo et al. (2019), which evaluated SMEs' perceptions and knowledge about financial reporting according to Financial Accounting Standards for SMEs to increase SMEs' access to bank financing and competitiveness. According to Indonesian banks, the study showed that only 22% of SMEs in Indonesia have access to credit financing. One of the substantial challenges they face is a poor financial administration and management system.

While the AIS provides accurate financial data to trade partners/suppliers who give credit and examine the firm's creditworthiness which is the least indicator. According to the respondents, they pay their suppliers in cash because the latter offer discounts and other freebies. Additionally, suppliers are quite cautious about their business's credit condition. However, some SMEs are considering paying their trade suppliers on account, mainly if the transaction is recurring, to optimize the use of their cash and other liquid assets and put aside funds for past-due expenses and obligations.

It was corroborated by Hezabr's (2018) research, which demonstrates that merchants who are responsive to customer needs have a major competitive advantage in the market. The AIS aids financial accounting and planning. Retailers and suppliers must collaborate to increase supply chain efficiency. AIS is critical for enhancing merchant-supplier relationships because it facilitates cross-system financial and accounting data sharing.

Performance Improvement. The highest indicator, accounting information system facilitates owners/managers to understand their work better and reduce ambiguity (Table 5). It got a weighted mean of 4.84 and an interpretation of strongly agree. Followed by AIS provides budget and performance reports, which received a weighted mean of 4.83 and an interpretation of strongly agree. In comparison, AIS's assistance in assessing payments and projecting workforce requirements received the lowest weighted score of 4.48. The overall weighted mean average for performance improvement is 4.72, which corresponds to a strong agreement.

Table 5. Implications of SMEs' Accounting Information System to Financial Decision Making along Performance Improvement

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. AIS tracks daily spending promptly and generates pertinent financial information that assists the firm in determining whether they have already been over its budget.	4.78	SA
2. It helps owners/managers better understand their activities and eliminate uncertainty before making choices.	4.84	SA

3. It is a vital element for generating reliable financial data that can be used to assess costs and allocate resources effectively and efficiently.	4.69	SA
4. It gives financial data that may be utilized to compute reduced product/service costs and establish if a product's quality generates a profit.	4.76	SA
5. It accelerates data collection, processing, and storing by producing reliable financial statements.	4.82	SA
6. It collects data on the actual sales and market position of new items to serve as the foundation for any action.	4.52	SA
7. It aids the firm in guaranteeing that enough human, mechanical, and material resources are available at the proper moment to make the items or offer the service.	4.67	SA
8. It assists the firm in determining its manufacturing capacity, cost-cutting program, and inventory management.	4.80	SA
9. It generates budget and performance reports that compare expected and actual outcomes to determine if the business process is currently functioning over the budgeted amount.	4.83	SA
10. It assists in assessing payments and calculating the manpower required to satisfy production needs through total costs and a table of workers'/employees' wages.	4.48	SA
Average Weighted Mean	4.72	SA

Legend:

- 4.21-5.00 - Strongly Agree (SA) 1.81-2.60 – Disagree (D)
- 3.41-4.20 - Agree (A) 1.01-1.80 – Strongly Disagree (SD)
- 2.61-3.40 - Neither Agree nor Disagree (NA or D)

According to the table, an AIS enables owners/managers to understand their responsibilities better and eliminate confusion before making business-related choices. According to the respondents, AIS enables the generation of reliable, comparable, and high-quality financial data/reports. Additionally, financial information aids in decision-making, especially when paired with improved performance assessments and business strategies.

It was corroborated by the study of Siyanbola et al. (2019), which found that the AIS had a significant positive effect on the SME performance. Additionally, it was established that the AIS used by

small business managers/owners benefited them in their decision-making and business performance. Consequently, the authors recommended that users of accounting information be aware of the AIS quality available to aid them in performing and making financial decisions.

Budget and performance reports are provided by AIS, which is the second-highest result. According to respondents, budget and performance reports are critical for their business's operation. These enable them to manage their finances for the next months or years based on their organization's strategy and performance results.

As with Okour's (2016) study, AIS should be utilized to plan and manage a firm's operations. Budgeting is achievable in a variety of situations. It must be adopted to get the full benefits of the system. However, for full utilization of the AIS, it might need enhancements to offer vital information to management for future decisions. Additionally, AIS can also assist in the budgeting process. Budgeting is critical to the success of the business and should be emphasized.

Test for Significant Relationship between the SMEs Business Profile and the Implication of AIS to Financial Decision Making

The Somer's Delta Correlation Coefficient (D) was used to examine the link between the respondents' profile in terms of total assets in 2020, the number of staff and years in operation, and the financial decision-making implications of the SMEs AIS. Additionally, the Rank Biserial Correlation Coefficient (rrb) was utilized to ascertain the association between the respondents' profiles and the type of accounting information system employed. Table 6 summarizes the results at 5% significance level.

The findings imply that the null hypothesis about total assets in 2020 and the financial decision-making implications of SMEs' AIS is rejected. There is a weak positive correlation between the variables, as shown by Somer's Delta coefficient $D = 0.129$ with a p-value of 0.008. There is no significant relationship between the number of years in operation and the implication of AIS to financial decision-making with Somer's Delta coefficient $D = -0,001$. Also, there is no significant association between respondents' type of AIS utilized to

the financial decision-making implications of SMEs’ AIS with Rank Biserial Correlation Coefficient $r_{rb} = 0.032$ and $r_{rb} = 0.049$. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

The null hypothesis is rejected between total assets in 2020 and the implications of AIS to financial decision-making. According to the respondents, when their assets increase, they become more cautious in their financial actions, sometimes out of fear of losing business resources. It was corroborated by Akhtar and Liu’s (2018) study, which indicated a weak correlation between the owner’s financial information and their financial decisions. Firms with more assets may be more prone to make financial statement-based judgments than firms with fewer assets.

Table 6. Relationship between Profile of SMEs and the Implication of the SMEs Accounting Information System to Financial Decision-Making

Profile	Business Strategy		Performance Improvement		Implication	
	Test Statistic	p-value	Test Statistic	p-value	Test Statistic	p-value
Total assets in 2020	D = 0.144	0.007*	D = 0.159	0.006*	D = 0.129	0.008*
Number of years in operation	D = -0.008	0.856	D = 0.004	0.935	D = -0.001	0.985
Type of accounting information system being used	$r_{rb} = 0.069$	0.418	$r_{rb} = 0.032$	0.707	$r_{rb} = 0.049$	0.567

**significant at 0.05*

The null hypothesis is accepted between the number of years in operation, and the type of AIS used to the implications of AIS to financial decision-making. However, an institution's decision-making and work activities necessitate various AIS. Most AIS must connect functional-level data and business processes to produce relevant decision-making information (Ayabei, 2017).

Moreover, in Pirayesh et al. (2018) ’s study, enhancing the quality of the AIS enables owners or managers to make more informed business decisions. It demonstrated the effect of AIS on

management choices on the one hand and the influence of quality features on management decisions on the other. According to the results, accounting software improves the quality of financial information and, as a result, the quality of organizations' financial decision-making. Similarly, it helps enhance the quality of financial accounting data and reports. The preparation of financial reports and their relevance, reliability, understandability, and comparability are critical components of making effective financial decisions.

Proposed Strategies to Improve the Quality of Financial Decision-Making of SMEs in Daet, Camarines Norte

The proposed strategies addressed the primary accounting information system issues confronting SMEs based on the implications of AIS on financial decision-making in business strategy and performance improvement. Additionally, it integrated the researchers' recommendations for improving the AIS's decision-making capabilities. There is a need to monitor and assess potential improvements to SMEs' AIS. These strategies cover various issues, including concerns, objectives, tactics, and other factors.

Table 7 outlines proposed strategies for improving SMEs' financial decision-making quality. The recommended strategies focus on providing financial reports to internal and external users, ensuring appropriate human machinery and material resources in business operation and production, and the basis of intervention on new product sales and market status.

Table 7. Strategies to Improve the Quality of Financial Decision-Making of Small and Medium Enterprises in Daet, Camarines Norte

AREA OF CONCERN	OBJECTIVE	PROPOSED ACTIVITIES/ STRATEGIES	EXPECTED OUTCOME
Implement AIS that fits the business needs of SMEs, particularly in production/providing services, and can intervene in sales and market status and other important aspects of business operation.	To identify the AIS that fits the needs of SMEs that are essential to their business operation.	Looking for suitable video courses on optimizing the use of their current AIS such as MS Excel, Google Spreadsheet tutorials, and other alternatives that concentrate on financial decision-making	
Utilize the use of new/existing AIS in providing financial reports to internal and external users.	To provide financial reports with the use of new or existing AIS that will assist internal and external users in having quality financial decision-making.	Look for or outsource an AIS provider with client support and training such as QuickBooks, Xero, and others. Hire financial analyst and AIS experts Solicit support from the local government, DTI, or educational institutions for AIS and financial analysis seminars/training.	Effective and efficient AIS that will result in quality financial decision-making

The option that might be taken is to use and outsource AIS to a provider specializing in serving SMEs’ needs. Additionally, it must be affordable, easy to use, and simple to maintain. It also must be safe and capable of multi-business support capabilities, including automated financial report generation and analysis. Financial statement analysis is a critical procedure that must be completed in order to make sound decisions.

It is supported by the study of Hasanaj & Kuqi (2019) that financial analysis and accounting information serve as the foundation for making internal and external choices. It can determine

its financial position, how it has performed throughout the periods under consideration, and future trends in that company by analyzing financial documents. Additionally, it can seek suppliers that provide customer support and training. This activity is crucial to the smooth and effective implementation of a well-designed AIS and the realization of its worth.

Additionally, it is vital that personnel be aware of and trained in its use. This leads to accurate and consistent accounting information, allowing better and faster decision-making and performance improvement. Moreover, it will ensure the right labor and material resources are available to generate or provide services and help as the basis of intervention on new product sales and market status. To implement the aforementioned approaches, owners, managers, and employees of SMEs, accounting software providers, the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI), local government units (LGUs), the Bureau of Internal Revenue (BIR), industry, and educational institutions must cooperate.

Chong and Nizam (2017) also discovered that deploying an AIS enhances a firm's performance and capability to undertake a sound business strategy. This study revealed a statistically significant relationship between accounting software and SMEs' success, indicating that having accurate and reliable accounting information advantages organizational effectiveness and that the AIS affects performance.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Most of the respondents are small entities with total assets of P3,000,000 to P100,000,000 in 2020, are in crucial years of business operation of 3 to 5 years, and used a manual accounting information system on their business operation.
2. AIS produces financial reports for bank loan approval, capital accumulation, and business development, which significantly support the implications of AIS on financial decision-making

in business strategy. It provides credible financial accounts to external auditors and taxes authorities to avoid fines. It also provides intelligible and comparative financial statistics that help firms expand and produce high-quality products at affordable production costs. It also analyzes cost, sales, and income data to produce timely and appropriate financial reports for government monitoring and trade partners/suppliers that offer credit. Hence, the respondents strongly agreed that AIS has implications for their financial decision-making in terms of business strategy.

Moreover, budget and performance reports, help owners/managers comprehend their duties and reduce ambiguity, and expedite financial data collection, processing, and storage. It also helps businesses determine their production capacities and inventory, record daily expenses for budgeting, and calculate lower costs. Measuring income helps the organization ensure that enough human, equipment, and material resources are available, acts as a critical tool for producing reliable financial data to analyze costs for cost distribution, and helps evaluate payment and predict the future. Hence, the respondents strongly agreed that AIS has implications for their financial decision-making in terms of performance improvement.

3. This study rejected the null hypothesis and discovered a weak positive association between respondents' total assets in 2020 and the implications of SMEs' AIS to financial-decision making. However, the null hypothesis was accepted that the type of AIS utilized and years in operation had no significant relationship to the implications of AIS to financial decision-making.
4. The study proposed strategies to improve SMEs' quality of financial decision-making in Daet, Camarines Norte.

The following recommendations were made in light of the study's findings:

1. As most SMEs in Daet, Camarines Norte are in their crucial years and have considerable capital, they may acquire and deploy a computerized AIS/accounting software that suits their requirements and budget or optimize the usage of their current accounting information system. Thus, innovative AIS for good

financial decision-making makes them more competitive.

2. SMEs must consider using AIS, which is essential in their business strategies and performance enhancements. Particularly in generating financial reports that are available to internal and external users, aligned with their business operations and productions, and valuable as the basis of intervention on new product sales and market status.
3. SMEs may engage with the DTI, LGUs, the BIR, or educational institutions to develop a high-quality accounting information system to be deployed, and adhering to stricter accounting standards and having more effective internal control will substantially influence the firm to properly account for and safeguard all of their assets and resources.
4. SMEs may adopt the proposed strategies to improve their financial decision-making. They may outsource or acquire cost-effective, simple-to-use accounting software, secure and includes multi-business capabilities such as automatic financial report generation and analysis, as well as end-user support and training. Additionally, businesses may engage experts in AIS and financial analysts to help them make better financial decisions.

Moreover, SMEs may expand their engagement and collaborations with the government, private sector, NGOs, and educational institutions to provide AIS and financial analysis training and seminars. The DTI, local governments, BIR, and educational institutions may collaborate to develop initiatives that address the needs of SMEs.

5. Future researchers may research the development of a computerized AIS or accounting software that will meet SMEs' demands in producing high-quality, cost-effective, and timely financial information or statements to assist them in their financial decision-making.

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